

many plants in several crosses was delayed despite the short-day treatment. Some plants in crosses such as G. Benton 1101/IR42, DA29/IR42, and BR4/Patnai 23 matured as late as 134 days after sowing.

A study of the parents showed that crosses involving two parents of long basic vegetative phase (BVP) (such as G. Benton 1101/IR42 and DA29/IR42) resulted in delayed flowering of many lines (see table). But in crosses where one or both parents have short BVP, such as Silewah/Hokkai 241, the resulting progeny are early flowering.

The delay in flowering of certain crosses is mostly the result of long BVP. Thus, a line with a BVP of 60 days will take longer than 100 days to mature. Such crosses tend to diminish the advantage of RGA because the possibility of 3 generations/year becomes difficult.

The BVP, if known, should be consi-

Basic vegetative phase (BVP) and growth duration of varieties involved in crosses. IRRI, 1981.

	BVP	Growth duration (days)
G. Benton 1101	60	F ₂ = 122
IR42	49	F ₃ = 99
DA29	41	F ₂ = 113
IR42	49	F ₃ = 134
BR4	40	F ₂ = 115
Patnai 23	41	F ₃ = 106
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 82
Hokkai 241	13	F ₃ = 67
		F ₄ = 70
		F ₅ = 75
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 85
IR2793-80-1/ IR747B2-6-3	short	
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 103
IR52	medium	

dered in determining what crosses to run through RGA. Crosses with long BVP that are insensitive to photoperiod could be planted in the field because the growth duration in the RGA is not considerably shortened and, in some cases, is actually delayed. ■

Performance of IR36 in Karnataka, India

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In Karnataka, about 55% of the rice area is planted to 16 recommended high yielding varieties. Some more area could be brought under high yielding rices by filling the extension gap. But special varieties with multiple resistance, interme-

diated plant stature, and earliness are needed for the area still planted to native rices.

Recent research and minikit results have indicated that IR36 has potential to supplement the currently recommended early-maturing, high-yielding varieties. IR36 has four attractive features: long slender grain, tolerance for salinity, tolerance for iron deficiency, and early maturity. This combination of characteristics cannot be found in any variety on the current recommended list.

Performance of IR36 in Karnataka, South India, 1978-80.

Year	Season	Variety ^a	Sites ^b (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over check varieties
1978	Wet	IR36	5	5.1	
		Rasi		4.7	9
		IR20		4.6	11
		Ratna		4.2	21
1978	Upland trial	IR36	1	4.8	
		Rasi		4.4	9
1979	Wet	IR36	3	4.4	—
		Mandya Vani		3.9	13
		IR20		4.4	—
		Pushpa		4.0	10
1980	Wet	IR36	1	4.1	
		Madhu		3.8	8
		Pushpa		3.3	24

^aSome check varieties were not included at all sites. ^bMandya, Mangalore, Mugad, Dhadesugur, Hebbal, Nagenahalli, and Ankoal, Karnataka, India.

Performance tests conducted at different sites and across seasons in the rice experiment stations of Karnataka show the superiority of IR36 over Rasi, Ratna, Mandya Vani, Madhu, IR20, and Pushpa (see table).

IR36 also was evaluated for two seasons through minikit trials in farmers' fields and will be tested for a third season. It is hoped that IR36 will supplement other early varieties in the districts of Bangalore, Tumkur, Kolar, Chitradurga, Bellary, Raichur, Shimoga, and Dharwad. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Aflatoxins in Sri Lankan rice

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Carcinogenic aflatoxins are produced by the fungi *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus* that commonly grow on cereals and legumes in tropical climates. In Sri Lanka, rice is mainly consumed as raw *kekulu* processed (with or without bran) or parboiled rice (brown or polished). In parboiling, rough rice is soaked, steamed and sun-dried before milling. The chances of grains becoming moldy during this procedure are high. Various types of rice were examined for the relationship of processing method to aflatoxin contamination.

About 27% of the rough rice samples collected from Kandy were contami-

Occurrence of aflatoxin B₁ in Sri Lankan rice.

Rice	B ₁ (ppm)	Rice class
BG90-2	0	rough
BG94-1	0	rough
BG400-1	trace +	rough
BG379-2	0	rough
BG34-8	0.056	rough
MI39-193-1	0	rough
MI639-124-23	0	rough
MI290-32	0	rough
BW265	0.024	rough
BW272-6B	0	rough
BW272-8	0	rough
Parboiled samba	0	polished
Parboiled	0.128	polished
Parboiled	0.234	brown rice